

BIOMEDICAL ENGINEERING IN THE AGE OF AI: APPLICATIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a revolutionary field of computer science that integrates human intelligence into machines, allowing them to perform human tasks successfully. It has influenced many areas, including Biomedical Engineering (BME). The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) with BME hopes to boost accuracy in diagnostics, personal treatment programs, and improve research in medicine. This study focuses on exploring about “Biomedical Engineering in The Age of AI: Applications and Implications”. It also deals with its capabilities of AI, Phrases of growth in BME, the evolution of AI, its application in the field of BME, its role and potential implications for healthcare. A thorough examination of the latest research was carried out to gain knowledge about applications of artificial intelligence in BME, with a focus on medical imaging, cancer diagnosis and treatment, advancements in plastic surgery, tissue engineering, robot-assisted surgeries, stroke and dementia diagnosis, and personalized medicine. The application of AI in BME not only increases clinical efficiency and accuracy, but it additionally has the potential to decrease healthcare costs and increase access to high-quality care. However, problems like privacy of information, security, efficiency, and biases caused by algorithms must be overcome in order to fully take advantage of these benefits. It is important to recognize that AI is not designed to totally replace humans, at least in the next few years, but rather help them. Humans need to collaborate collectively to obtain precise diagnoses and treatment. Future research should focus on improving the quality of data, solving ethical issues, and exploring the connection between AI and other emerging technologies in BME.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Biomedical Engineering , security

I. Introduction

Netflix, voice assistants such Alexa, surveillance, Google's AlphaGo, and the machine that organizes our belongings are a few examples of artificial intelligence. However, what precisely is Artificial Intelligence? Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a revolutionary field of computer science that integrates human intelligence into machines, allowing them to perform human tasks successfully. The main aim of AI is to comprehend, think, and respond to every new situation based on previous experience without programming explicitly. French mathematician and inventor Blaise Pascal built the first mechanically calculating machine in 1642. In 1955, John McCarthy, a young American mathematician and computer scientist coined the term “Artificial Intelligence” for a summer conference at Dartmouth University which he organized. Due to many obstacles, evolution wasn't visible during the early stages. These limitations were overcome in the beginning of the 2000s because of Deep Learning and Machine Learning. AI has numerous applications in medicine, including diagnosis, surgery, and even more. AI is used in biomedical engineering to improve telemedicine, personalized treatments, continuous surveillance, and speed and accuracy. Top hospitals such as Cleveland Clinic as well as large health-tech companies such as Siemens and Philips invest a huge amount of money in Data Science and AI. Many

papers available explain how AI is fundamentally altering the landscape of healthcare in ways previously unexplored. This paper gives you an even better idea of the role of AI in Biomedical Engineering.

A. Categories of AI based on their capabilities:

AI can be divided into several categories based on their capabilities. They are Narrow AI, General AI, and Superintelligent AI. Narrow AI known as Weak AI as its name says is weak and is limited to a narrow area and can perform only programmed tasks. Voice assistants like Alexa and Siri, language translation systems, Netflix, and image recognition software all have demonstrated excellent results in increasing Narrow AI. While some might say that Alexa is not a weak AI because it can complete a lot of things, it is important to highlight that it only concludes defined tasks based on the specific given word. This brings us to the next category called General AI or Strong AI. This is the capability of machines to pick up a skill that humans can. We are halfway successful in implementing this phase. IBM Watson, OpenAI, and GPT-3 all fall under this category. The third category is Superintelligent AI, which is a stage where machines are passed on with superior cognitive abilities of humans just like you have seen in science fiction movies. Scientists are currently working hard to achieve this level. As of now, Narrow AI is only used in Biomedical and various other fields of study. It has advanced the field of biomedicine, but they are specialized and lack understanding.

B. Evolution of Artificial Intelligence:

Over the years, the use of "artificial intelligence" has shown a consistent increase. It has attained its peak between 2005 and 2008, followed by a decline (shown in Figure 1). This decline may have been due to limitations in computing power. However, since 2016, with the consistent increase in computing power, there has been a renewed surge in the use of artificial intelligence, as evidenced by the increased occurrence of related search terms such as "machine learning", "artificial intelligence", "neural network", and "deep learning," [6]

Figure 1: Artificial Intelligence in the biomedical Literature 1980-2020

C. Disease studied with AI:

When we search for "artificial intelligence" in the Embase database (Excerpta Medica database; a biomedical and pharmacological bibliographic database), we find 48,141 results. Searching for "machine learning" yields 76,765 results. We can use the "explosion" option to include all more specific terms without entering them individually. When we search for "'machine learning'/exp OR 'artificial intelligence'/exp," we get 289,055 results. We can find the full list of search terms using Emtree search. Additionally, we can examine the disorders mentioned in the publications. The top 20 results (given in figure 2) show that "breast cancer" is the most commonly mentioned, followed by "Alzheimer disease" and "COVID-19". The top 20 results include

oncological diseases, neurological disorders, diabetes diseases, cardiovascular diseases, drug cytotoxicity, and inflammation (refer to Figure 2). There are also four brain problems, three diabetes diseases, and two cardiovascular diseases, along with drug cytotoxicity and inflammation. [6]

Figure 2 : Disease in 'Artificial Intelligence' publications

D. Applications of AI in Biomedical Engineering:

AI plays a prominent role in the Biomedical Engineering Sector. A few examples are listed below:

- It analyzes medical images accuracy
- Machine learning models helps to predict the patient's condition
- It assists in surgeries
- It uses natural language to gather information from clinical notes.
- It has personalized patient outcomes

II. AI in Biomedical Engineering:

A. Biomedical Imaging through Artificial Intelligence:

Medical imaging is a rapidly developing discipline which utilizes artificial intelligence to improve healthcare diagnostics. AI has improved considerably as the number of techniques used for medical imaging has increased. AI has made significant advancements in medical image processing, particularly in automated retinal disease assessment (ARDA) for diseases like retinopathy of premature birth, diabetic retinopathy, and age-related macular degeneration. While solutions based on artificial intelligence show promise, it is essential to overcome the obstacles caused by data availability and their interpretability for successful utilization them.[1]

Brain imaging techniques such as MRI and PET provide an thorough understanding of problems in brain functioning and connectivity, but processing this data requires new technology. Combining artificial intelligence and brain imaging has an opportunity to improve the lives of patients. Deep learning techniques and the sine-cosine frequency grey wolf optimization

(SCFGWO) algorithm are utilized to detect and classify brain cancers. Each of these techniques have been proved to be effective using multiple metrics. This technique has an opportunity to improve patient care while also improving neuroscience.[1]

Lung imaging is currently gaining importance, especially for the identification and monitoring of COVID-19. In an important paper [4], the main focus is on developing artificial information to mimic actual information for lung CT in COVID-19 diagnosis. The similarity in structure index (SSIM), the peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR), and Fréchet inception distance (FID) indicate the fact that artificial pictures generated using the suggested method are very similar to original images. To minimize biases in machine learning (ML) models, a new modification method is utilized that doesn't require major changes to the neural network design, making it simple to use. This method works beyond COVID-19 diagnosis, and may have application in other picture patterns and imaging methods. Future research may investigate its applicability for different diseases and its connection with developing AI. [4]

B. In the cancer diagnosis and treatment:

Diagnosing cancer from images and tissue samples is highly complicated and time-consuming process. One of the major reasons is the limitless diversity of cancer cells. Every cancer has unique elements and every piece of tissue that the pathologist get is unique in some way or the other. It has features you may not have seen before. The evaluation is a hands-on, labour-intensive process. For one patient, a pathologist might study numerous tissues slides and consider variables like the density, shape, and number of cells. When analysing images, radiologists measure the size of tumours and draw outlines around them. According to Alexander T. Pearson, MD, PhD, an associate professor of clinical medicine at the University of Chicago, the Department of the biological sciences, when doctors develop data to improve the cancer treatment plan, "it may involve five sub-specialists to analyses the data" and reach an evidence-based outcome.[3]

When several diagnoses are seen, the evaluation of the pictures where the medical diagnosis may be less obvious varies from one doctor another. The problem of "interobserver variability" is when different doctors obtain different results from the same information is discussed in research regarding improving the accuracy of cancer detection. This does not imply that cancer diagnoses are never incorrect. It implies that even with the use of advanced imaging technologies for medicine that see into the human body, understanding what those pictures imply remains an interpretive human task.

So, AI is being used to provide another interpretation, offering a deeper analysis and precise identification of abnormalities in images. AI-assisted imaging offers several important benefits for cancer detection and treatment. It helps in better assessment of cancer risk, leading to earlier detection and treatment. Additionally, it determines effective treatment plans, reduces unnecessary biopsies, and minimizes false positive diagnoses. The technology accelerates the assessment process, allowing swift results and prioritization of high-risk cases. Ultimately, it has the potential to help us see the streamline workflows and free up healthcare professionals to help focus on complex cases.[3]

Lung imaging has attracted extensive research interest due to the aggressive nature of lung cancer. A recent study focused on accurately segmenting lung fields in chest X-ray images (as shown in figure 3) using super pixel resizing and encoder–decoder segmentation networks. The study effectively addressed challenges associated with lung field segmentation and highlighted the potential of deep learning techniques for semantic segmentation tasks. The method demonstrated high effectiveness compared to other approaches, as assessed using various evaluation metrics such as the Dice similarity coefficient, Jaccard index, sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy.[1]

Breast cancer, the second most reported cancer worldwide, requires early diagnosis. In the study [2], an AI-based approach evaluates the effectiveness of two computer-aided detection (CAD) systems for differentiating between malignant and benign breast lesions using radiomics and deep transfer learning. The findings indicate that deep transfer learning can effectively extract meaningful features from medical images, even with limited training data, offering more discriminatory information than traditional

handcrafted radiomics features. However, the need for explainability in artificial intelligence and medical decision systems must be further explored.

C. Advancement in Plastic Surgery using Machine Learning:

With ever increasing of electronic data collected in the health care, scientists are considering the use of a sub field of artificial intelligence - Machine learning to improve medical care and patient outcomes. An analysis of machine learning can contribute to advancements in plastic surgery. Machine learning analyses historical data to evolve algorithms capable of knowledge acquisition. Projects with healthcare applications that include IBM Watson Health cognitive computing system. Authors have some areas where machine learning can improve efficiency and clinical outcomes – Burn surgery, Micro surgery, craniofacial surgery, hand and peripheral nerve surgery, aesthetic surgery. Authors also expect useful applications of machine learning to improve plastic surgery training. Nevertheless, they concentrate the need for measures to make sure the safety and clinical relevance of the results collected by machine learning and also remember at the same time that computer generated algorithms cannot replace the trained human eye yet. [11, 12] With ever increasing of electronic data collected in the health care, scientists are considering the use of a sub field of artificial intelligence - Machine learning to improve medical care and patient outcomes. An analysis of machine learning can contribute to advancements in plastic surgery. Machine learning analyses historical data to evolve algorithms capable of knowledge acquisition.

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Figure 3 : AI assisted cancer diagnosis imaging

The Increasing amount of electronic data in healthcare has led to use machine learning in order to improve medical healthcare. For plastic surgery, machine learning helps in analyzing historical data and evolving algorithms. IBM Watson healthcare is one of the projects that has shown the potential in improving efficiency and clinical outcomes in areas of burn surgery, microsurgery, hand and peripheral nerve surgery. It is important to prioritize the safety and clinical similarities of the results

collected by machine learning. It has to be recognized that computer-generated algorithms cannot replace the trained human eye yet. [6,7]

D. Advancement in Diagnosis of Stroke and Dementia:

One of the common causes of dementia and stroke is identified through a brain scan. This is possible with the help of Machine Learning. It does more accurately than current methods. Advanced software developed by experts at Imperial College London and the University of Edinburgh was able to detect and measure the severity of small vessel diseases, which are common causes of stroke and dementia. Scientists explain that this technology helps physicians in implementing the best treatment for patients during emergency settings. They are also capable of predicting a person's likelihood of developing dementia. This development also paves the way for personalized medicine. [8,9]

E. AI in Tissue Engineering:

The important part of medical research and clinical applications are Tissue Engineering. It aims to regenerate damaged organs. It encounters challenges in designing complex 3D structures by combining stem cells, biochemical factors, and biomaterials. Artificial intelligence improves tissue engineering by computer modelling, biological material design, cell growth improvement, and personalised treatment. AI is used in organ tissue engineering (bone, heart, nerve, skin, cartilage), employing various machine learning algorithms for data analysis, prediction, and optimization. [12]

F. Robots assisted Surgery:

The use of robotics in surgery is a significant advancement of India. More than 12,800 surgeries have been performed by 500 skilled robotic surgeons using the da Vinci Surgical System. This technology's computer vision provides detailed patient information. This enhances surgical performance. Robotics have also shown improvements in other areas of healthcare, such as rehabilitation, patient interaction, and logistical operations. These advancements show the wide-ranging benefits of integrating robotics into the healthcare sector.

III. Limitations Artificial Intelligence in Health Service

A. Data bias:

Large number of data is required to train the AI models in healthcare sector. Bias may occur when the data used for training does not reflect the specific data required and when insufficient data is used to train AI models. For example, to social discrimination (lack access to services health) and relatively small samples (for example, minority groups). [12]

B. Personal:

One of the most sensitive information that can be owned by an individual about another is Health Service Data. In the case of health care, the privacy of an individual is highly secured because privacy is bound by patient autonomy, personal identity and well-being. Thus, it is ethically important to respect patients' confidentiality. This has to be taken into consideration due to the implementation of AI in Health Care. [10]

C. Problem of ethic related to research and biomedical:

Biomedical ethical principles must be followed by AI in healthcare. These include elements like consent, privacy, safety, voluntary participation, and autonomous decision-making, and are crucial for any application.[13]

IV. Countries Performing Research in AI

The countries that do a greater number of AI research can be calculated by Embase Database. The figure shows the occurrences of the search terms like ‘artificial intelligence’ or ‘machine learning’ in conjunction with the names of the top 20 global economies in the ‘affiliation’ field. The China and the USA occupies the second and first largest economies, respectively. It is followed at a distance by South Korea, the UK, and Canada, which are ranked at 10th, 5th, and 9th in terms of economies. The lowest rankings are assigned to Saudi Arabia with 178 publications and Indonesia with 191 publications. These findings align closely with the 2020 Nature Index analysis. Both the data’s show that the USA and China are at the leading positions. The differences between the Nature Index and Embase Database rankings may be due to factors such as the time span of the analysis, or the specific search queries used to find AI publications. These differences should be taken into account when interpreting the rankings and drawing conclusions about the distribution of AI research across different countries. [5]

Figure 4: Artificial Intelligence in the top 20 global economies

V. Discussions

This review shows the wide application of Artificial Intelligence in the field of Biomedical Engineering, problems faced due to the use of AI, and it also shows the exponential rate at which it is growing. AI seems to be used mostly for diagnosis and treatment. COVID-19 is already in the top-3 of diseases studied using AI, which shows the large influence the COVID-19 pandemic has on medical field [6]. More amount of AI research has to be published by countries like China, the United States, South Korea, the United Kingdom and Canada. China, USA and UK are not surprising under consideration, since these countries have many of the world’s best educational institutions. But South Korea and Canada surprisingly appeared to be very productive in AI research. Stanford University is the world’s leading university in AI research at the current moment. Possible reasons for the wide range of applications are image classification and segmentation, object detection, video processing, natural language processing, speech recognition, etc. [1,2,4] This review only shows results from the PubMed and Embase databases. PubMed and Embase mostly include English publications. More advanced analyses and studies should be done to predict the direction in which the AI will

develop over the coming years. AI is expected to keep on growing at a high speed because the computers are fast enough to execute complex algorithms. Heterogeneous diseases such as cancer studies can be profited enormously from the algorithms. [3,4] AI will therefore be an important component in enabling accurate medicine. There are also recent developments that might Help in the rise of AI. Federated learning is especially useful to study rare diseases. Recently, there has been a set of regulations announced by the European Commission about the use of AI, defining some high-risk application using AI, under which some medical areas such as robot-assisted surgery [11] also comes under. These high-risk application areas need to maintain a number of strict obligations around the quality of data, security, documentation, etc... Data's read by machines should be standardized using medical vocabularies. Another issue that might affect the use of AI in biomedical engineering and healthcare is bias [12]: Large number of data is required to train the AI models in healthcare sector. Therefore, Initiatives have to be taken where data from all over the world (from all genders, race, and many age groups) are combined into a central database produce results that are less biased. Next is privacy [10]: One of the most sensitive information that can be owned by an individual about another is Health Service Data. So, it has to be maintained and stored with concern without leaking the persons personal data. For non-experts, AI often seems like a black hole where a lot of data go into it and comes out through some 'black magic'. Finally, it is important to realize that AI is not meant to completely replace humans, atleast, in the near future, but to help them. Humans should be supported by AI and should collaborate to reach precise diagnoses and treatment.

VI. Conclusion

In conclusion, Artificial Intelligence has the potential to transform Biomedical Engineering by improving diagnostic accuracy, personalizing treatment plans, and advancing medical research. AI in medicine is still developing as a diagnostic tool. It can sometimes create false information and images based on misunderstanding, but this might improve over time. The integration of AI in BME not only enhances clinical outcomes but also paves the way for more innovative and efficient healthcare solutions, ultimately benefiting patients and healthcare providers alike. There are brain disorders, diabetic diseases cardiovascular diseases, drug cytotoxicity and inflammation that are studied through AI. There are also various countries and Universities that are performing Research works in this field. AI tools could make oncology imaging more accessible in places with few specialists. The value of AI-assisted cancer diagnoses will be measured by the impact on patient health. As Artificial Intelligence continues to develop, it is important for researchers, clinicians, and policymakers to collaborate and ensure the responsible and effective integration of AI technologies in Biomedical Engineering. Therefore, it has to be taken care to not only look at their applications in the field but also to care about the problems like that of maintaining the privacy information, avoiding the data bias, safety, efficacy, decision-making, the costs and access to all people. Future research should focus on enhancing data quality, addressing ethical concerns, and exploring the synergy between AI and other emerging technologies in BME.

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